

Syntheses of 1,5-Benzothiazepines. Part-XI. Syntheses of 4-(4-Ethoxyanilino)-2-methyl-8-substituted-1,5-benzothiazepines

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2,4-Disubstituted-1,5-benzodiazepine compounds possess various biological activities¹. By comparing the structures of 1,4- and 1,5-benzodiazepines vis-à-vis 1,5-benzothiazepines, it is observed that despite the absence of any substituent in the fused benzene ring, 1,5-benzothiazepine class of drugs show intensive cardiovascular² and psychopharmacological³ properties, while chemotherapeutic properties are exhibited only by 1,4- and 1,5-benzodiazepines possessing a substituent in the fused benzene ring⁴.

Assumption of the presence of 5-*N*-substitution and 2-(*p*-alkoxyphenyl) group besides the presence of 4-oxo group in 1,5-benzothiazepine nucleus⁵ is attributed to impart the bioactivity in diltiazem. We report here the syntheses of 2-methyl-1,5-benzothiazepines having *p*-ethoxyphenylamino substitution at 4- and halogeno, alkyl and alkoxy at position-8.

Substituted-2-amino-benzenethiols (1a-f) with acetoacet-4-ethoxyanilide (2) in ethanol containing traces of glacial acetic acid undergo dehydrative cyclisation to give the corresponding 1,5-benzothiazepines (3a-f) in a single-step process in satisfactory yields.

In the ir spectra, the bands at 1 690–1 650, 1 570–1 530 and ~ 700 cm⁻¹ (amide bands) and two bands near 3 520 and 3 400 cm⁻² (stretching NH₂ were absent which negated the formation of an intermediate). Instead, the characteristic⁶ bands were observed at 1 610–1 602 (C=N) and 1 255–1 230, 1 060–1 045 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C). The secondary amino group was indicated by the presence of a band at 3 300–3 200 cm⁻¹ (N–H) while its deformation vibrations caused the absorption at 1 520–1 510 cm⁻¹.

All the ¹H nmr spectra showed absorptions char-

acteristic of the ethoxyl group at δ 1.2–1.36 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz) and 3.84–4.24 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz). A singlet at δ 1.96–2.24 integrating for three protons in all the spectra, was assigned to the C-2 methyl group. The aromatic region, besides showing a multiplet integrating for seven aromatic protons (δ 6.24–7.38), also showed a singlet corresponding to one proton at δ 6.12–6.28 due to C-3 proton and a broad N–H signal at around δ 8.24–8.36. The spectra of 3d, 3e and 3f also showed the characteristic methyl, methoxyl and ethoxyl signals at δ 1.92 (s), 3.72 (s) and (1.24 t, 4.08 q, *J* 7 Hz respectively). The mass spectrum of 3e showed *M*⁺ peak at *m/z* 340, clusters of isotopic peaks at *m/z* 344, 346, 348 and at 388, 390, 392 were obtained for *M*⁺, [*M*+2]⁺ and [*M*+4]⁺ of 3b and 3c. The intensity of [*M*+2]⁺ peak of 3b was nearly one-third of the *M*⁺ peak while that of 3c was almost equal to that of the *M*⁺ peak which confirmed the presence of chlorine and bromine in 3b and 3c respectively.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer infracord-577 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Jeol FT NMR spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

The 5-substituted-2-amino-benzenethiols (1a-f) were prepared by reported methods⁷.

Acetoacet-4-ethoxyanilide (2) : An equimolar (0.1 mol) mixture of ethyl acetoacetate (13.0 ml) and *p*-phenitidine (16.9 ml) was refluxed for 15 min. The alcohol formed was removed by distillation and the residue washed repeatedly with diethyl ether. The resulting solid on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid

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|-----------|---------------------------------------|
| a. X = I | d. X = CH ₃ |
| b. X = Cl | e. X = OCH ₃ |
| c. X = Br | f. X = OC ₂ H ₅ |

gave long shining colourless needles (13.48 g, 68%) m. p. 134° (lit.⁸ 130–35°).

4-(4-Ethoxyanilino)-8-methoxy-2-methyl-1,5-benzothiazepine (3e): A mixture of 2-amino-5-methoxybenzenethiol (1e: 0.001 mol) and acetoacet-4-ethoxyanilide (2: 0.001 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (10.0 ml) containing glacial acetic acid (1.0 ml) for 3 h when the reaction mixture turned dark blue. Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure gave a black residue which on crystallisation from methanol gave blue-black crystals (0.207g, 61%), m.p. 172°.

Compounds 3a-d and 3f (m.p. 210, 224, 220, 188 and 175° respectively) were similarly prepared in 50–65% yields with satisfactory elemental analyses.

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References

1. F. GIORDANO, C. GRIECO, C. SILIPO and A. VITTORIS, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **84**, 174411; D. P. CLIFORD, D. JACKSON, R. V. EDWARD and P. JEFFREY, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1977, **87**, 146947; J. R. DEBAUN, F. M. PALLOS and D. R. BAKER, US Pat., 3 947 475/1976 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **85**, 21492); A. I. KRAVCHENKO, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1974, **81**, 145638.
2. C. R. ETINGIN and D. P. HAJJAR, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1990, **112**, 91510.
3. E. R. Squibb and Sons Inc., *Chem. Abstr.*, 1990, **112**, 125223.
4. L. C. RANDALL in "Psychopharmacological Agents", ed. M. GORDEN, Academic, New York, 1964; L. O. RANDALI and B. KAPELI, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1961, **8**, 15; S. L. C. RAYMOND, J. L. VICTOR, B. C. TSING and E. K. MAUREEN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **106**, 277465; J. ROELINE, K. GABBR and R. MICHAEL, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1987, **106**, 43821; B. J. HUNT, A. J. GEORGE and A. P. RIDGES, *Br. J. Chem. Pharmacol.*, 1974, **1**, 174; R. D. HEILMAN, E. W. BAUER and J. P. BAVENZO, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1975, **82**, 106282.
5. M. MIYAZAKI, T. IWAKUMA and T. TANAKA, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1973, **21**, 92.
6. A. LEVAI and R. BOGNAR, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. (Hung.)*, 1976, **88**, 293; 1977, **92**, 415.
7. R. C. BREVIS HER and P. B. DAINS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 1364.
8. G. V. JADHAV, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 669.